

Air purifiers in classrooms of infection control – a pilot study: An interim descriptive analysis before publication of the statistical analysis plan

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Prior to the initiation of a large, randomized trial investigating the impact of implementing air purifiers equipped with High-Efficiency Particulate Air (HEPA) filters in Norwegian primary schools, the Centre for Epidemic Intervention Research (CEIR) and SINTEF undertook a pilot study to assess the acceptability and feasibility of placing ceiling mounted versus portable air purifiers in classroom settings across six Norwegian primary institutions. The protocol for this pilot study has been published elsewhere¹. The present document describes an interim descriptive analysis of air quality measurements, and the rationale behind the decision to undertake this analysis prior to the dissemination of the statistical analysis plan.

About the pilot study

The pilot study was conducted from week 5 to week 15 in the winter of 2024. As part of this study, portable and ceiling mounted air purifiers was installed in three classrooms in one school. The three classrooms rotated weekly whether the air purifiers were on or off, so that every third week the classroom would have either ceiling mounted air purifier on, portable air purifier on or no air purification.

Timeline

CEIR intends to perform the large, randomized trial during the autumn/winter 2024/2025. To obtain ethical approval from the Regional Ethics Committee in time, the study team is required to submit an application encompassing a study protocol on the 19th of March 2024. We considered it important that the protocol included some preliminary descriptive statistics from the pilot study, showing air quality in classrooms with ceiling mounted air purifiers versus portable air purifiers versus no air purifiers. The study team has yet to release a complete statistical analysis plan for the pilot phase as of the 19th of March 2024. To maintain complete transparency, this document thus describes the preliminary interim descriptive analysis intended to be incorporated within the trial protocol to be submitted to the Regional Ethics Committee.

Analysis

- We will conduct an interim descriptive analysis of air quality measurements from two different sensors in each classroom encompassing the entire trial period.
- Plot 1: Boxplot PM 2.5 count by air purification
 - o We will compare three states (ceiling-mounted, portable and none)
 - o We will include measurements taken during school hours in the three classrooms where air purification was tested (school hours 9 to 15)
 - o We will include measurements from all six sensors (two in each classroom)
- Plot 2: Boxplots PM 2.5 count by air purification and sensor
 - o We will compare three states (ceiling-mounted, portable and none) by sensor

- We will include measurements taken during school hours in the three classrooms where air purification was tested (school hours 9 to 15)
- We will analyse data from the two sensors separately
- Plot 3: Boxplot PM 2.5 count by air purification vs no airpurification
 - We will compare two states (ceiling-mounted or portable vs no airpurification)
 - We will include measurements taken during school hours in the three classrooms where air purification was tested (school hours 9 to 15)
 - We will analyse data from the two sensors separately
- Plot 4: Boxplot PM 2.5 count by air purification vs no airpurification and sensor
 - We will compare two states (ceiling-mounted or portable vs no airpurification) by sensor
 - We will include measurements taken during school hours in the three classrooms where air purification was tested (school hours 9 to 15)
 - We will analyse data from the two sensors separately

We will also tabulate some descriptive statistics (mean sd etc.) by group.

References

1. Cathinka Halle Julin RBS, Ingeborg Hess Elgersma, Petter Elstrøm, Christine Holst, Arnfinn Helleve, Atle Fretheim , Sverre B. Holøs. Study Protocol: Air purifiers in classrooms for infection control - a pilot study: DOI <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10526801>. 2024